

DCH Folder Structure Guidelines

Version 1.0.0

1. Separate types of information
2. Separate stages of processing (e.g. raw, cleaned, annotated)
3. Keep the folder depth at 4–5 levels
4. Order folders with leading numbers in folder names
5. Document your folder structure

1 Separate types of information

Separate types of information, including project and administrative information.

```
Example:  project/
          ├── 01_project_management/
          ├── 02_data/
          ├── 03_analysis/
          └── 04_publications/
```

2 Separate stages of processing

Separate different states of the data.

```
Example:  ─ 02_data/
          ├── 01_raw_data/
          ├── 02_cleaned_data/
          └── 03_annotated_data/
```

3 Keep the folder depth at 4–5 levels

Avoid too deeply nested folder hierarchies by keeping the depth to 4–5 levels.

4 Order folders with leading numbers in folder names

Begin folder names on all levels with padded numbers to facilitate sorting.

```
Example : ─ 03_analysis/
          ├── 01_skript/
          └── 02_output/
```

5 Document your folder structure

Document your folder structure in a README file placed in the top folder of the dataset.

See: DCH Readme File Guidelines [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7447616](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447616)